

Research Article

AI narratives of job displacement on social media and their influence on engineering undergraduates' future employment views

B. R. Ajayi-Owoyemi *

Department of General studies, School of Physical Science, Federal University of Technology, Akure , Nigeria

Abstract

AI technologies have become increasingly capable of performing tasks that are traditionally known to be carried out by Engineers. As a result, there are concerns about the potential displacement of engineering jobs. These concerns are constantly disseminated and amplified on social media platforms. Exposure to these narratives of job displacement may pose emotional issues for young people, especially undergraduates who are active users and whose main information outlet is social media. This study is guided by three research questions: examine the extent to which engineering students are exposed to AI narratives of job displacement on social media; the extent to which these AI narratives on social media influence engineering students' perceptions toward future employment; and evaluate the behavioural responses of students resulting from their engagement with AI job-related content online. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted using an online questionnaire administered to 400 engineering students at the Federal University of Technology, Akure. Instrument reliability assessed with Cronbach's alpha, produced a coefficient of 0.81, reflecting strong internal consistency. The findings reveal widespread exposure to AI job displacement content, particularly on YouTube, Facebook, and TikTok.. While a notable proportion of students express concern, many also report optimism and proactive responses such as skill acquisition and career adaptation. The study concludes that although AI-related narratives elicit mixed emotional reactions, they are prompting significant engagement with upskilling and career realignment among future engineers. Recommendations are made for higher education institutions and policymakers to embed AI literacy and digital resilience into engineering curricula.

Keywords: AI Narratives, Engineering Undergraduates, Job displacement, Employment views, Social media.

1. Introduction

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology is changing the way people live, work and communicate in the twenty-first century. A lot of people still find it unfathomable that computer systems or technologies can successfully carry out the tasks that require human efforts or intelligence. Artificial intelligence has permeated almost all sectors of human endeavours, from education to transportation, to finance, building technology, health care, communication, and engineering (Yadav and Shrawankar, 2025), so much that it has been predicted over and again that many traditional jobs will cease to exist in few years to come.

Artificial intelligence systems can learn from existing data and improve their performance, analyse and provide solutions to complex problems, interpret and understand data from sensors, images and other sources. Now, there are

chatbots that can handle customer enquiries, provide supports and resolve issues without any human input. Customer services executives are now being replaced by virtual assistants. Jobs that require data entry and processing are being taken over by AI. Content creation now requires less human involvement as AI can create content such as news article, social media posts and even product description. While the emergence of AI has sparked optimism and hope in some economic and social quarters, it has also triggered or rekindle concerns about job displacement on a very largescale (George, 2024).

Narratives are an essential prerequisite to societal change and the way narratives are woven and spread around concerning issues of public interest depend largely on the opinions people hold about such issues (Ash, 2025). The

*Corresponding author: B. R. Ajayi-Owoyemi

Email: bushine2004@gmail.com (B. R. Ajayi-Owoyemi)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7393-759X>

Received: 24/10/2025; Accepted: 15/11/2025; Published: 30/11/2025

stories audiences are exposed to, read or seen in the media could influence perceptions, interactions and shape their opinions. Of particular interest is the social media which has continued to dominate public engagement, even as it becomes the main source of obtaining information by young people (Rheingold, 2008). A study by Liao (2024) demonstrates how content shared, especially on platforms like X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, and TikTok can reinforce echo chambers, manipulate perceptions, and alter public sentiments.

One of the narratives being spread around on social media is that of AI and jobs displacement in the nearest future. Such narratives include how AI is set to displace a lot of people from their jobs, how automation will take over the world employment space, how a lot of courses offered in the universities would become redundant, among others. According to Ash (2025), these narratives and the perspectives they uphold, are problematic for workers everywhere. Patel (2025) opines that since AI is replacing roles that involve repetitive tasks and daily routines, this has affected many lives negatively in many companies due to job displacement and many have had to rethink their employment prospects and structure.

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has introduced a paradigm shift in the global labour market especially with fields such as manufacturing and engineering. This is because AI technologies have become increasingly capable of performing tasks that are traditionally known to be carried out by Engineers. These tasks range from automated design processes, predictive maintenance, data analysis and optimization, infrastructure and tools design and maintenance among others. As a result, there is a subtle growing concern about the displacement of engineering jobs (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2020). These concerns are constantly amplified and disseminated on social media platforms. The narratives, most times, are over-saturated and embellished with fictitious facts which may pose emotional issues for young people, especially undergraduates who are active users and whose main news or information outlet is the social media. Also, most public discourse around AI is usually captured in extremity, either of utopian efficiency or dystopian displacements which contributes greatly to anxiety or confusion among future professionals (Elish and Watkins, 2020)

Social media such as LinkedIn, X and Youtube play a very significant role in shaping opinions as students frequently engage with trending topics such as AI's influence and job displacement (Walker, Dillard-Wright, and Iradukunda, 2023). Cave et al (2019) found out that young people who are exposed to AI job-loss narratives are likely to feel disconnected from employment realities. Scott, Marcu, Anderson, Newman and Schoenebeck (2023) opined that exposure to AI content on digital platforms may be linked to increased anxiety about job security and empowerment. These narratives could negatively influence engineering undergraduates' motivation and perceptions about job prospects towards their future in the engineering field

(Fisher, 2024).

There are existing studies on the growing relevance of AI but a significant gap remains in empirical investigations that quantitatively assess the relationship between exposure to AI-generated narratives and changes in public opinion (Nasiri and Hashemzadeh, 2025), particularly how engineering students perceive and interpret AI narratives of job displacement on social media, the lack of this insight could make the engineering undergraduates nurse misinformed ideas or notion about AI's impact on their employment prospect. This study therefore, sets out to examine AI narratives of job displacement on social media and the influence they have on the employment perceptions of engineering undergraduates.

This study aims to investigate how AI narratives of Job displacement on social media influence engineering students' employment perceptions. The specific objectives are to;

- i. determine the extent of exposure of engineering undergraduates to AI-narratives of job displacement on social media.
- ii. assess the influence of these narratives on students' perceptions, emotions, and attitudes toward future employment
- iii. evaluate students' behavioral responses to AI-related employment concerns on social media

The following research questions were examined in this study:

1. To what extent are engineering students exposed to AI narratives of job displacement on social media?
2. How do narratives of job displacement on social media influence engineering students' perception towards future employment?
3. What behavioral responses do engineering undergraduates exhibit as a result of their exposure to AI narratives of job displacement on social media?

2. Literature Review

Many studies have predicted the global transformational effects of AI on future jobs. Frey and Osborne revealed that nearly 47% of the jobs in the United States are at a high risk of automation, most especially those that involves routines. One question, however remains critical and should be addressed as such: Is AI and automation the same? Automation involves rule-based, repetitive task execution while AI systems simulate human intelligence through adaptive learning and complex decision-making (Dahlin, 2024). So, AI disruption tendencies extend to skilled professions such as engineering, accounting, healthcare and more, where tasks once considered purely human, are now susceptible to algorithmic substitution. (Rawashdeh, 2025).

AI and its framing in public discourse is also receiving considerable attention. While some narratives emphasize opportunities, innovation and efficiency, others emphasize displacement, unemployment and redundancy. George (2024) distinguishes between 'job shifting' and 'job loss' narratives arguing that framing significantly influences how audience

respond to AI related change. On social media where information is most times emotionally charged and sensationalized, such narratives can create confusion, fear or apathy among young people. Fisher (2024) observes that social media platforms often amplify dystopian themes, particularly around job loss, thereby creating heightened anxiety and distorted expectations about the future of work.

Undergraduates who are immersed in digital media may be susceptible to these narratives. Rheingold (2008) observes that participatory media shapes not only how young people consume information, but also how they interpret their roles as future professionals. Walker, Dillard-Wright, and Iradukunda (2023) argue that algorithm bias and emotionally salient content can affect perceptions of AI capabilities and risks. Also, Can, Gözde & Tolay, Ebru (2019) found out that overtime exposure to AI job loss narratives can lead to disillusionment and emotional disengagement among youths, Scott, Marcu, Anderson, Newman and Schoeneberk (2023) linked such exposure to heightened anxiety about job security.

Although AI may displace certain jobs in the future, it also creates demand for new competences and skills such as data science, machine learning and AI ethics. Studies reveal that exposure to AI narratives can prompt adaptive behaviours including upskilling and career adjustment. Wang and Lu (2025) assert that workers who frequently use the internet or work remotely are more likely to perceive AI threats and consequently take proactive steps as a reaction. Also, Schmidpeter and Winter-Ebmer (2021) corroborate the importance of continuous skills development in order to maintain workforce relevance. Among students, such responses would not only expose risk awareness but also portray a growing need to align with AI related or integrated industries.

This study is situated in framing theory, and it originates from media studies. The theory suggests that the way a particular news or information is presented or 'framed' could influence the audiences' perceptions and that the media focuses attention on certain events and then places them within a field of meaning. A frame refers to the way media and media gatekeepers organize and present the events and issues they cover, and the interpretation of the meaning that the audience makes of it. Frames influence the perception of the news of the audience, it presents how the audience perceives certain events or information. Deetz, Tracy and Simpson (2000) explain that framing a subject or information could give it a positive or negative connotation.

AI narratives that emphasizes job loss and redundancy may spark up fear, worries and anxieties, while those that highlight opportunity, innovations and the need for digital skills may inspire optimism and proactiveness. The framing theory suggests that the emotional and cognitive responses that AI narratives on social media elicit from the engineering undergraduates depend largely on the content and how they are presented.

3. Methodology

The study was conducted at the Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA), located in Ondo State, Nigeria. FUTA is one of Nigeria's leading technological universities and has a strong emphasis on engineering and applied sciences. The study was carried out in a virtual environment using an online questionnaire administered via Google Forms. This mode of data collection was selected to facilitate ease of distribution, ensure anonymity, and allow for quick data collection, especially among a tech-savvy student population accustomed to digital platforms. The questionnaire link was distributed through university-managed social media groups (WhatsApp, Telegram) with necessary ethical consent and participation guidelines obtained.

3.1. Research Design

This research adopts a descriptive cross-sectional survey design, which is suitable for assessing the current opinions, perceptions, and behavioral tendencies of a defined population at a single point in time. The design enabled the researcher to collect quantitative data on exposure to AI narratives, emotional and perceptual responses, and behavioral intentions related to employment among engineering students. The study population consists of all undergraduate students in engineering disciplines at FUTA. The engineering students were selected due to their potential exposure to discourse on technology and automation, a profession which has been predicted to be taken over by AI.

3.2. Instrument of Data Collection

The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed and hosted on Google Forms. The items included multiple-choice, Likert scale, and checkbox questions to allow for frequency-based and perception-based analysis. The instrument was pre-tested with 20 students for clarity, reliability, and time efficiency, and adjustments were made accordingly. Content validity was ensured by reviewing the questionnaire with experts in communication studies and one in educational technology. Their feedback helped refine the clarity and appropriateness of the items. Reliability of the instrument was measured using Cronbach's Alpha, and the pilot test results yielded a coefficient of 0.81, indicating high internal consistency.

A sample size of 400 respondents was targeted using purposive sampling. This number is considered adequate for quantitative analysis and to ensure a representative distribution across various levels and departments. Inclusion criteria were: (i) being a registered engineering undergraduate at FUTA, and (ii) consenting to participate in the online survey. Respondents were assured of confidentiality and anonymity.

3.3. Data Analyses

The data collected through the Google Form were initially exported into Microsoft Excel for proper sorting,

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	15 - 18	38	9.5
	19 - 22	187	46.8
	23 - 26	141	35.3
	27 - 30	21	5.3
	30 and above	13	3.3
	Total		400
Gender	Female	59	14.8
	Male	341	85.3
	Total	400	100.0
Current Level	100	50	12.5
	300	100	25.0
	500	250	62.5
	Total	400	100.0
Field of Study	AGE	49	12.3
	BME	5	1.3
	CEE	50	12.5
	CPE	9	2.3
	CVE	31	7.8
	EEE	7	1.8
	ICE	4	1.0
	IPE	18	4.5
	MCE	46	11.5
	MEE	75	18.8
	MME	84	21.0
	MNE	22	5.5
	Total	400	100.0

cleaning, and organization. Thereafter, the cleaned dataset was imported into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26 for comprehensive statistical analysis, Chi-square tests was used to examine relationships between demographic variables. All results were interpreted at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

4. Results

This section presents results of data analysed in this study.

The demographic table shows that the majority of respondents are between the ages of 19–22 (46.8%) and 23–26 (35.3%), indicating a largely young adult population.

Most participants are male (85.3%), with females only 14.8%, this is consistent with the male-dominated nature of engineering disciplines in Nigeria.. Most students are in their final year (500 level – 62.5%) suggesting that majority of the respondents are actively considering their future career. The respondents come from diverse engineering disciplines, with Metallurgical and Materials Engineering (21.0%), Mechanical Engineering (18.8%), and Civil and Environmental Engineering (12.5%) being the most represented.

4.1. Answers to Research Questions

4.1.1 Research Question 1

Research Question 1 *To what extent are engineering students exposed to AI narratives of job displacement on social media?.*

*Corresponding author: B. R. Ajayi-Owoyemi

Email: bushine2004@gmail.com (B. R. Ajayi-Owoyemi)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7393-759X>

Received: 24/10/2025; **Accepted:** 15/11/2025; **Published:** 30/11/2025

Table 2: Students' Exposure to AI and AI Narratives on Social Media

Item	Response Category	Frequency	Percentage
How often do you come across content on social media discussing artificial intelligence?	Frequently	165	41.3
	Never	2	.5
	Occasionally	110	27.5
	Rarely	33	8.3
	Very Frequently	90	22.5
	Total	400	100.0
How often do you come across content on social media discussing artificial intelligence and its present impact on jobs and employment opportunities?	Frequently	149	37.3
	Never	4	1.0
	Occasionally	115	28.7
	Rarely	65	16.3
	Very Frequently	67	16.8
	Total	400	100.0
How would you describe the tone of most AI-related job content you see on social media?	Emphasizing Opportunities (Positive)	188	47.0
	Emphasizing Threats (Negative)	50	12.5
	Neutral	68	17.0
	Purely Informational	94	23.5
	Total	400	100.0

This table reveals how frequently engineering students see content about Artificial Intelligence (AI) on social media particularly regarding how AI may affect the engineering profession in the future. It also reveals how they perceive the tone of the posts. A substantial proportion of students reported frequent encounters with AI-related content. 41.3% frequently, and 22.5% very frequently, encountered general AI content. Also, 37.3% frequently, and 16.8% very

frequently specifically encountered content about AI displacing jobs. On the tone of the AI-related content, 47% described the tone of the content as being positive and opportunity-revealing, 23.5% consider the tone as merely informational and 12.5% described the tone as being negative or threatening. This reveals a mixed but mostly optimistic framing of AI narratives on their social media spaces.

Table 3: Platforms of Exposure to AI Job Narratives and Their Emotional Reactions

Item	Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Which social media platform do you mostly see AI job-related content?	Facebook	145	20.6%
	Twitter/X	1	0.1%
	Instagram	134	19.0%
	Tiktok	158	22.4%
	LinkedIn	83	11.8%
	Youtube	163	23.2%
	Whatsapp	9	1.3%
	Snapchat	1	0.1%
	Pinterest	1	0.1%
	Discord	2	0.3%
	Telegram	3	0.4%
	Reddit	1	0.1%
	FHG	2	0.3%
	Total	704	100.0%
What kind of feeling or emotion do these AI content on future job displacement elicit from you?	Concerned	111	27.8%
	Optimism	169	42.3%
	Worry	47	11.8%
	Indifference	24	6.0%
	Uncertainty	49	12.3%
	Total	400	100.0%

The table provides data regarding the key social media channels where engineering students come across AI-related content of job displacement, as well as the feelings these encounters elicit. According to the results, respondents mostly encountered AI job-related narratives on YouTube (23.2%), TikTok (22.4%), and Facebook (20.6%), This reveals that the respondents predominantly engage with AI narratives through these visual and interactive social media platforms. The emotional responses that the AI content on job displacement elicit from them vary: 42.3% were

optimistic and 27.8% were concerned, 11.8% were worried and 12.3% were indifferent, indicating that while the respondents were optimistic about AI's potentials in providing more job opportunities, they were also concerned about the displacement of jobs by AI.

4.1.2. Research Question 2

Research Question 2: *How do narratives of job displacement on social media influence engineering students' perception towards future employment?*

Table 4: Students' Perceptions of AI and Future Employment and Behavioural Responses

Item	Response Category	Frequency	Percent
AI is likely to reduce job opportunities for undergraduates.	Agree	181	45.3
	Disagree	47	11.8
	Neutral	87	21.8
	Strongly Agree	69	17.3
	Strongly Disagree	16	4.0
	Total	400	100.0
I feel uncertain about my future career due to AI-related posts online	Agree	70	17.5
	Disagree	148	37.0
	Neutral	98	24.5
	Strongly Agree	21	5.3
	Strongly Disagree	63	15.8
	Total	400	100.0
Social media influences how I perceive AI and employment prospects	Agree	201	50.2
	Disagree	57	14.2
	Neutral	81	20.3
	Strongly Agree	46	11.5
	Strongly Disagree	15	3.8
	Total	400	100.0
I am motivated to acquire new skills due to AI job discussions online.	Agree	218	54.5
	Disagree	12	3.0
	Neutral	44	11.0
	Strongly Agree	123	30.8
	Strongly Disagree	3	.8
	Total	400	100.0

This table highlights respondents' perceptions and attitudes about AI's content about job displacement on social media. 45.3% of respondents agreed that AI may reduce job opportunities for undergraduates in the future, indicating a possibility of AI taking over engineering jobs in the nearest

future, 50% agreed and 11.5% strongly agreed that social media influences their perceptions about AI and future career. 85.3% indicated that AI narratives online have motivated them to acquire new skills. These findings recommend a proactive, rather than a passive approach to

*Corresponding author: B. R. Ajayi-Owoyemi

Email: bushine2004@gmail.com (B. R. Ajayi-Owoyemi)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7393-759X>

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AI's expanding position on future employment.

engineering undergraduates exhibit as a result of their exposure to AI narratives of job displacement on social media?

4.1.3. Research Question 3

Research Question 3: *What behavioral responses do*

Table 5: Students' Behavioral Responses and Career Plans as a Response to AI Job-Related Content on Social Media

Item	Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Have you enrolled in any of these due to AI-related job concerns on social media?	Bootcamps or workshops	27	6.8
	None of the above	107	26.8
	Online courses (e.g., Coursera, Udemy)	100	25.0
	Self-study (YouTube, blogs, etc.)	143	35.8
	University-organized tech programs	23	5.8
	Total	400	100.0
How would you rate your preparedness for employment in an AI-driven future?	Neutral	128	32.0
	Not prepared at all	9	2.3
	Not very prepared	55	13.8
	Somewhat prepared	122	30.5
	Very prepared	86	21.5
Total	400	100.0	
What is your current plan regarding careers in light of AI's impact?	I am unsure about my career direction due to AI	14	3.5
	I plan to stick to my original career path regardless of AI	77	19.3
	I want to combine my field with AI skills	245	61.3
	I want to pursue a career in AI/tech	64	16.0
	Total	400	100.0

This table summarizes respondents' behavioral responses and future career ambitions as influenced by AI-related job content on social media. The respondents expressed a proactive behaviour as they participated in self-study via Youtube/blogs (35.8%); online courses like Coursera/Udemy (25.0%) and Bootcamps/workshops (6.8%). In terms of preparedness for an AI-driven future, 30.5% feel somewhat

prepared and 21.5% feel very prepared, the rest were either unprepared or neutral. When asked about their career plan, 61.3% planned to integrate their field with AI skills, 16.0% intend to pursue a career in AI/tech while only 3.5% expressed uncertainty about their career directions due to AI narratives.

Table 6: Chi-Square Tests for Associations Between Perceptions of AI and Socio-Demographic Variables

Statement	Demographic Variable	χ^2	df	p-value
AI is likely to reduce job opportunities for undergraduates.	Current Level	10.90	8	.207
	Field of Study	63.50	44	.029
	Gender	14.86	4	.005
I feel uncertain about my future career due to AI-related posts online	Current Level	6.16	8	.630
	Field of Study	57.83	44	.079
	Gender	3.62	4	.460
Social media influences how I perceive AI and employment prospects	Current Level	10.90	8	.208
	Field of Study	72.99	44	.004
	Gender	13.63	4	.009

Note. χ^2 = Pearson chi-square value. p-values are 2-tailed.

4.2. Discussion

This study explored how engineering students at the Federal University of Technology, Akure interact with social media narratives on Artificial Intelligence and job

displacement, and how these narratives influence their perceptions, emotions and their career behaviours. The findings from this study provide insights into how narratives on digital media, particularly how those that are amplified on

social media could influence the students' perceptions and attitudes towards their future career in the engineering profession.

To examine the extent to which the engineering students are exposed to AI job-related narratives on social media. The results show that a significant number of the students are frequently exposed to such narratives, particularly through the highly visual and algorithm-driven platforms like YouTube, TikTok and Facebook. This stance is confirmed by Umoh (2024) and Liao (2024) who assert that social media is now a dominant means of information among young people, and that it is shaping how they interpret various societal issues like AI and the future of jobs. Based on the framing theory used for this study, this exposure matters mostly because of the way the narratives are constructed. According to Deetz (2000), media frames make certain aspects of an issue gain attention, which in this case is AI's perceived threat to employment, while minimizing attention on others. The implication of this is that students are not merely absorbing information, they are interpreting their future relevance in engineering profession through the lens of social media narratives.

On the emotional responses that these narratives elicited from the students, they reflect a sort of a dual engagement of anxiety and resilience. While some students reported feelings of concern, worry and uncertainty, the most common response is that of optimism. This complex emotional response aligns with Fisher (2024) and Scott et al (2023) who observed that AI related narrative often generates mixed feelings of excitement and uncertainty at the same time. Notably, the emotional responses that the narratives elicited did not meet passiveness, rather, the emotion appeared to have served as motivation, prompting many of the students to seek out other learning opportunities or even consider their career paths. This reflects a psychological coping mechanism where anxiety could prompt action rather than total avoidance.

The most encouraging outcome of this study, perhaps, is the proactiveness demonstrated by majority of the respondents. Most of the respondents reported being motivated to acquire new skills as a response to AI-related job discussions. This means that while there was concern about AI reducing jobs opportunities, students were not passive in the face of this threat, they, instead, engaged themselves in upskilling through self-study, online courses and bootcamps. This supports the findings by Schmidpeter and Winter-Ebmer (2021), that emphasized the role of continuous training in mitigating the impact of AI disruption. This also aligns with Wang and Lu's (2025) assertion that digital exposure to AI threats can prompt proactive responses, even among young people. Interestingly, while the motivation level was high, few of them reported that they were prepared for an AI driven future. This discrepancy between their motivation level and actual readiness suggests a gap between formal support structures including mentoring

and institutional guidance. Chen, Li and Tang (2022) argue that without proper digital training and access to structured programmes, motivation may not translate into real preparedness for AI future work environments.

The findings also reveal that the students have a career plan as a significant majority of the respondents, instead of abandoning their current aspirations in engineering, indicated a desire to integrate AI related skills into their existing fields. Some other respondents planned a full transition into AI industries. This represents a conscious plan of career paths in the light of AI technological transformation. From the framing theory perspective, this suggests that students are actively resisting fear-based narratives and favouring opportunity-based narratives. These students are reframing the AI narratives from a narrative of job displacement to that of job adaptation and resilience which are critical ingredients for success in the evolving job markets.

The study also found out that students' perceptions were associated with gender and field of study. This is supported by Wang and Lu's work (2025) that revealed that demographic variables influence perceived risk of AI induced displacement. Male and female respondents, along some specific disciplines view AI narratives in different ways. These views may have stemmed from variety in exposure, pre-existing career expectations or even identity-based interpretations of technological change. Framing theory also comes into play here that the same narrative may be viewed or interpreted differently based on one's prior knowledge and experiences, and also emotional investment.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated how engineering students engage with social media narratives of AI-induced job displacement and how such narratives influence their perceptions, emotional responses and behavioural attitudes regarding their future employment. The findings revealed a digitally engaged student population that is widely exposed to AI related employment narratives, primarily through YouTube, TikTok and Facebook. While some of the students expressed anxiety and concern over the impact of AI on their future job prospects, many also expressed optimism and demonstrate proactiveness which include upskilling through online courses, self-study and career planning that integrates AI related skills and competences. These behaviours reflect a sense of adaptability and resilience among the engineering students.

However, the study highlights a disconnect between motivation and perceived preparedness for AI future jobs. While many of the students were eager to learn, they feel inadequately ready to transition into fully AI-integrated job market. This gap calls for institutional and policy-level interventions to embed AI education early into the university curriculum, support students' access to quality training and guidance to navigate their way into AI driven world of employments. Ultimately, this study underscores the critical

role of media narratives in shaping employment perceptions and the need for higher institutions to step up their responsibility in equipping students for an AI future that is already unfolding.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AGE	Agricultural Engineering
BME	Biomedical Engineering
CEE	Chemical Engineering
CPE	Computer Engineering
CVE	Civil Engineering
EEE	Electrical and Electronics Engineering
ICE	Information and Communications Engineering
IPE	Industrial Productions Engineering
MCE	Mechatronics Engineering
MEE	Mechanical Engineering
MME	Material and Metallurgical Engineering
MNE	Mining Engineering

Author Contributions

Ajayi-Owoyemi, Busayo Rebecca: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing- original draft, Analysis of result, Review and Editing.

Conflicts of Interest

The author(s) declare that they have no known competing financial interests, professional affiliations or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Funding

None

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